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Report on the impact of new representations of Islam and its (digital) spaces due to the development of mass- and fast mobility in global societies.

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Photographs from Mecca in an Era of Mass- and Fast Mobility

Rukayyah Reichling (ESR 13)

Mecca may be considered the geographical and spiritual centre of Islam. The city's sanctity stems from the presence of the sanctuary of the Ka'ba at its heart, which on nineteen different occasions in the Qur'an has been referred to as al-masjid al-haram. According to Islamic tradition, the Ka'ba, or baitullah, was originally built by the Prophet Abraham as the first place of worship to the One God. Its position determines the qibla, the direction of prayer for Muslims around the world. Places in and around Mecca, the "mother of cities", are furthermore the destination of the small and big Muslim pilgrimages. Considering the city's sanctity and that the paths of pilgrims from broad regions of the Islamic world meet in Mecca, it is little astonishing that in the early tradition of map-making, Muslim cartographers frequently placed Mecca at the geographical centre of the world.

Not only differs Mecca from other metropolises of the Muslim world in the light of its spiritual and physical meaning, but also in a different perspective: the city is considered

a Muslim-only space. This decree is based on a verse from the ninth Surah of the Qur'an, Al-Tawbah, in which "those who associate others with Allah in His Divinity" are established as "unclean". God therefore commands the Muslim community in the same verse to "not let them even go near the Sacred Mosque" (9:28). Even though this verse had been interpreted by different Islamic schools and scholars in varying ways, there has been a general consensus that Mecca should stay closed to non-Muslims. While images from the Ka'ba appeared in Islamic manuscripts, ceramic tiles or on printed hajj certificates, Europeans from non-Islamic faith could for centuries only make themselves a picture of Mecca based on travel reports from a limited number of adventurous travellers who had managed to enter the city, or based on scarce paintings of the city that circulated in the West.

With the development of mass- and fast mobility in the nineteenth century, the question of inclusion to and exclusion of Mecca became more pressing than ever. Since in

the last decades of the nineteenth century the vast majority of Muslim pilgrims to Mecca were colonial subjects, curiosity surrounding the holy city increased considerably in colonial circles. An account related in the Khulasa al-Kalam by Ahmad ibn Zayni Dahlan (1816-1886), a leading religious scholar in Mecca of the Shafi'i school, is a fine example reporting the colonial interest in the holy city of Islam. Dahlan explains that non-Muslim Europeans pressured the new Sharif of Mecca with the quest of being allowed to enter the holy realms. According to Dahlan's account, the Meccan Sharif reacted to this as follows: "When they asked me this, I was at a loss. They would not accept my answer that this was forbidden according to our law, and that the Muslims would not be content about it. But then God inspired me to give them a rational and convincing reply [jawaban 'aqliyyan iqna'iyyan]. I told them: You have seen pictures of Mecca on the maps and in the geographical publication [jughrafiyyat]. She [Mecca] features neither gardens nor rivers and there are no mosaics. If you went there, you would not

gain anything beyond what you have seen on the pictures and maps. I can say that it would require a great effort from you without providing benefits." This quote from Dahlan's book underlines the fact that, according to the Sharif, the city of Mecca has not to offer what European eyes are longing for: gardens, rivers and mosaics. Thereby, the account suggests that the city's real value, which lies in its spiritual force, cannot be grasped by those foreign Europeans whose vision is supposedly limited to the city's outer and aesthetic aspects.

Interestingly, Dahlan also mentions "pictures of Mecca" that could be seen in geographical publications. At the time when his Khulasa al-Kalam was published in the 1880s, photographs of Mecca were still an absolute rarity. Even though photography had been invented in 1839 and in the same year exported to the Arab world, Mecca did – in opposition to the Holy Land of Palestine – not figure among the early places that were photographed in the Middle East. The initial unavailability of pictures from Mecca was undoubtedly

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related to the forbidden character of Mecca to non-Muslims. As the medium of photography originated in the Western metropole Paris, Europeans were the first to produce, use and propagate this new technology. In its early decades, photography was employed by the leading European empires to encounter the world; it was used to “establish imperial power, extend imperial authority, reinforce imperial power, survey imperial possessions, demonstrate imperial connections, and articulate imperial identity”. Like other forms of modern technology, photography developed into a “tool of empire” that fortified the increasing Western domination of the globe. In the globalizing world of the long nineteenth century, the camera worked such as the technologies of steam and print as enabler of intensified and accelerated human interaction.

Even though Muslims were more and more subjected to the Western gaze, the new media were soon picked up by Muslim communities worldwide who adopted them for purposes that their initial inventors

and disseminators had never imagined.

In 1880, Mecca was brought into picture for the first time by the Egyptian officer Muhammad Sadiq Bey. Based on expert knowledge that he acquired at the renowned École Polytechnique in Paris, he became the president of the Société Khédivale de Géographie and was repeatedly sent on cartographic missions to the Hijaz. As guide of the hajj (amin al-surra), he twice accompanied the palanquin known as al-mahmal from Cairo to Mecca. After his hajj journeys he published the knowledge that he accumulated in the form of photographs, maps and diaries. Five years later, in 1885, Sadiq Bey was followed by the Dutchman Christiaan Snouck Hurgronje (1857-1936) who pro-forma converted to Islam and, in cooperation with a Meccan doctor called ‘Abd al-Ghaffar, asked pilgrims from all around the world to pose in front of his camera. With Snouck Hurgronje, photographs from Mecca reached a broad, well-educated audience outside the Muslim community.

Snouck published his written and visual material from Mecca in 1889, following a conference in Berlin in which he presented his ethnographic work at the Gesellschaft für Erdkunde. Sadiq Bey, Snouck Hurgronje and ‘Abdul Ghaffar, the three pioneering photographers of Mecca, were followed by a range of other photographers in the subsequent decennia, amongst which the general Ibrahim Rif’at Pasha, the official in the Ministry of Justice Muhammad ‘Ali Effendi Sa’udi, both Egyptians, and the Indian photographer H.A. Mirza. The development of new technologies in the 1880s such as small cameras and roll films – which were much more affordable and easy to use than their older dry-plate counterparts which required the use of sensitive glassplates and chemicals – paved the way for amateur photography in the Holy Places.

With such new equipment, the first commercial photographers started making photographs from Mecca and Medina to sell the prints locally or in their home towns. Also Sultan Abdülhamid II sent

out photographers to Mecca and Medina so as to produce images of the most treasured sites of his empire to be kept in his private collections of the Yıldız palace. Meccan images were used and re-used in print, while authorship continued to be, very much in the fashion of the day, mentioned in a volatile and elusive manner.

Photographs from Mecca did often not indicate the proper sources; and signatures that some of the photographs bore, did not forcibly refer to the original author. Within and without the Muslim community, pictures from Mecca circulated greatly, some via publications and family albums, others via postcards. The invention of photography which went hand in hand with the development of mass- and fast mobility thus allowed Muslims as well as non-Muslims to present Mecca, the geographical heart of Islam, in fundamentally novel ways. The emergence of Meccan photographs opened up the way for new social imaginaries of a global ummah, a Muslim community that is related to and united through its most holy city.

When Birds of a Feather Instagram together

Zeynep Aydin (ESR 14)

Introduction

In the twenty-first century the link between the words terrorism and Islam are undoubtedly established within society, politics, and (most of all) media. Especially social media is responsible for the shaping and forming of public opinion based on a new pattern of power relations and particularly the manifestation of Islam in the cyberworld (Aguilera-Carnerero and Azeez, 2016).

Social media exchange has been found to be particularly valuable for spreading far-right discourses far within the country of origin, but the far-right parties rarely engage in spreading their discourses transnationally (Froio and Ganesh, 2019). This is not to say however that racist, xenophobic, and especially Islamophobic posts do not have an international reach. Indeed, the vilification of Islam, for which western mainstream media played an important catalyst, grows strong in the fertile grounds of the cyberworld. Demonization of Muslims and

Islam is specifically attained on social media through the conceptual simplification of Muslims at large into terrorists. Through repetition, symbolic divergence, and euphemisms a symbolic construction of reality is promoted “under the conceptual simplification protagonist-antagonist, which causes the ‘other’” (Civila et al., 2020).

The debate today is no longer whether social media is an environment for cyber hate, but rather how hate is being transmitted and how this affects the image of Islam.

While the discourse of “echo chambers” have been studied at large and have been held responsible for a clear crystallization of different groups within the cyberworld that produce and reproduce shared beliefs (Sunstein, 2001). However, further research into the ever-evolving field of social media shows that it is not only selective exposure to that leads to attitude reinforcement. In fact, the exposure to opposing arguments achieves the very same result

and this phenomenon is known as “trench warfare”. It is the interplay of these mechanisms that shape the online discussion surrounding Islam that are at play after terror attacks perpetrated on western soil.

One main way in which the discussion of Islam online is taken up after traumatizing events, such as terror attacks, is through the use of hashtags. Hashtags illustrate this pattern beautifully and can be seen most clearly on Twitter and Instagram. Hashtags make posts searchable (Dorsch, 2018), archive messages for a(n advocacy) movement (Bruns and Burgess, 2011), and most importantly spread virally to other users of these social media platforms (Saxton et al., 2015). The use of hashtags thus transcends country boundaries and plays into both echo chambers, by addressing likeminded people, but should also encourage trench warfare, by presenting a controlled sphere in which to have arguments between islamophobes and those defending Islam. This paper extends on this work by

examining how the image of Islam is transmitted and changed on Instagram through the use of the hashtag #CharlieHebdo.

1. Hashtags and Ideology

Instagram has been found to have experienced a drastic increase in new users joining during the quarantine of the Covid-19 pandemic’s first wave (IAB Spain, 2020). Two important features that set Instagram and Twitter apart from other social media platforms is i) the flat hierarchy of the messaging system which does not rely on degrees of connection (i.e., family or friends), and ii) the use of hashtags which allow for the automatic aggregation of all posts with the same hashtag.

At its fundament, the hashtag is nothing more than a simple keyword formatted to act as a hypertext and could perform the same function without the hash-symbol. The deliberate inclusion of the symbol, however, distinguishes posts from regular text and is a conscious decision of the user to make the post

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searchable within a specific online discussion (Bruns, 2012). While hashtags seem fairly similar at face value, they do serve different purposes. Two of the main purposes that hashtags play have been found to be tie formation, by maintaining communities and self-representation, but also a way to assert ideological stances (Xu and Zhou, 2020).

The hashtags surrounding the Charlie Hebdo shooting, that appeared immediately after the attack, are a clear indicator of this particular phenomenon and can be viewed in a sort of spectrum of ideologies. The hashtag #JeSuisCharlie (I am Charlie) in particular was an endorsement of not only the satire magazine but also greatly focused on the fundamental right of freedom of expression. The reactionary hashtag #JeNeSuisCharlie (I am not Charlie) directly opposed the endorsement of the publication and freedom of speech when used for xenophobic or racist purposes. Another associated hashtag which gained much

attention was the #JeSuisAhmed (I am Ahmed) and refers back to one of the policemen killed in the terror attack. This hashtag is mainly made up of responses which try to differentiate between Islam and terror and raise the point that among those defending freedom of speech are also Muslims such as Ahmed (An et al., 2016).

While it can seem that hashtag use is a very exclusive means of communicating or linking posts on social media, it is very common to use a collection of hashtags in one single post. An overlap in hashtag use is a very frequent occurrence and can also be clearly witnessed in the overlap of both the #JeSuisCharlie and the #JeSuisAhmed hashtags in one post (ibid, 2016). In fact this phenomenon has been called the “inter-ideological mingling” and documents how the use of hashtags might help avoid homophily on social networking sites (Graham, 2016). This phenomenon has been found to consist of several strategies that are used especially by

white extremists to fuse right-wing extremist terms with more mainstream communication on social media sites and to gain greater exposure. The main strategies of these consist of the is done “joining” and “blending” strategies where extremist hashtags are joined haphazardly with trending hashtags or blended in a logical manner and with connections between the hashtags (ibid, 2016).

2. Echo Chambers and Extremism

One main theory that has been discussed extensively with regards to the impact of media has been the concept of echo chambers. Although this concept dates back to traditional media studies, it had gained much popularity with the onset of wide spread social media use. Echo chambers, or alternatively filter bubbles, refer to the consumption and contribution of and to media that is similar to ones own personal beliefs and views; which ultimately “creates positive feedback loops” for users (Jamieson and Cappella, 2008).

Social media especially is believed to be key in the creation of echo chambers, due to the makeup of some social media platforms (i.e. Facebook and Instagram) which “use algorithms that expose users to content based on previous preferences and behaviors” (Wahlström and Törnberg, 2019). It is proven however that echo chambers are most likely constructed around right-wing sentiments (Hmielowski et al., 2020) and that they are especially popular with right-wing populists and are used primarily to circumvent elitist media and law enforcement (Krämer, 2017).

While echo chambers are built based on political views or personal interest, it is trigger events such as terror attacks that reinforce these filter bubbles. ‘Tweets’ and ‘likes’, by so-called cybermobs, in turn boost negative sentiments like anti-Muslim hostility and can finally lead to real life targeting of Muslims (Awan, 2016).

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Analysis of echo chambers and especially right-wing populist ones have shown that Muslims are strongly vilified and almost always “represented as very violent, disparaging and extremist [and] as being strongly supportive of terrorism and attacks against America and the West” (Aguilera-Carnerero and Azeez, 2016). One danger that these types of echo chambers pose is the fact that they are able to normalize cyber hate speech against a perceived ‘out-group’ (Harel et al., 2020). Also, the fact that they make up their own definitions of terms such as ‘jihad’ and ‘islamist’ and can thus vilify the entire religion based on this new definition (Aguilera-Carnerero and Azeez, 2016).

Previous studies on echo chambers on social media have found that online platforms such as Twitter provide the ideal habitat for communication between far-right organizations and individuals harboring such sentiments. This is due to the minimal costs associated with sharing such posts and the range by which these posts can travel

in the shortest period of time (Davey and Ebner, 2017).

However, one major obstacle that far-right communication within the echo chamber, and thus the expansion of the echo chamber, faces is transnationalization. It has been proven that while anti-Muslim prejudiced tweets are the most likely posts to be shared transnationally, and are considered to be the “transnational glue of the far-right” (Froio and Ganesh, 2019), language constraints limit the degree of transnational communication (ibid, 2019). However, one recent development that social media platforms, such as Instagram and Twitter, are now implementing is the translate function that allows for captions of posts and tweets to be translated seamlessly with only one press of a button. This has the potential to bypass this issue and to ensure a higher rate of transnational communication.

3. Trench Warfare and Disconfirmation Bias

With the increasing amount that social media is being used, media studies are able to study its effects more thoroughly. While echo chambers were a very popular topic that was studied in the earlier years of the wide spread use of social media platforms. However, studies today prove that while individual still selectively expose themselves to information that they agree with more often they do not tend to disregard information and ideas that are conflicting to their own views (Dubois and Blank, 2018).

While echo chambers remain a long-disputed topic, new theories such as the trench warfare approach have surfaced. This approach focuses strongly on previous user bias rather than exclusively on the media surrounding of the user. Thus, “when people are presented with opposing arguments in online debates, these arguments may not make debaters question and alter their initial opinion but instead lead to a stronger belief

in the previous held opinion” (Karlsen et al., 2017). Therefore, it can be said that while people have a greater chance of meeting like-minded people through the help of the internet, it is this environment that biases users when they are faced with views that are in opposition to their own views.

The bias that is gained through constantly moving in like-minded spheres is well-established as confirmation bias whereas disconfirmation bias is thought to be created through trench warfare, i.e. the reinforcement through contradiction (ibid, 2017). Consequently, echo chambers and trench warfare do not negate each other, but can rather function alongside each other. So, while internet users grow their filter bubbles and create their echo chambers, trench warfare allows users to spar with users of opposing views and hashtags pose the necessary battle ground. Hashtags bring together those users that see a hashtag like a “virtual wearing of a team jersey” with those of opposing views and can lead to

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virtual battles called ‘tweet wars’ (Smith and Smith, 2012).

As discussed above the hashtags used after the Charlie Hebdo attack in 2015 is known to have been a platform on which opposing opinions clashed (Mondon and Winter, 2017a). Here the use of #JeSuisCharlie especially was flooded on one hand with exclams of Islamophobia and was countered by cries defending Islam. Islamophobic content has been shown to have been of two kinds namely illiberal and liberal Islamophobia. Illiberal Islamophobia is most like the traditional forms of racism known from the extreme far-right and is based on an exclusivist notion. Liberal Islamophobia works similarly by creating a stereotypical image of Islam (belief and culture) and Muslims as that which is “inherently opposed to some of the core values espoused in mythical and essentialized culturally homogenous, superior and enlightened West or Western nation” (Mondon and Winter, 2017b).

It was found that although the Charlie Hebdo attacks were used quite unevenly, throughout the Western nations, they were strongly tainted by right-wing Islamophobic content (ibid, 2017b). In fact, right-wing networks active behind Islamophobic content of hashtags like #JeSuisCharlie are so tight knit that they have in place common memes that they used in order to “mock common criticism of Islamophobia while simultaneously propagating hate speech” (Poole et al., 2020).

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Al-Andalus in the Eyes of the “New Religious Intellectuals”

Mounir Saifi (ESR 15)

Both globalization and digitization had certainly had an impact on Islam and the ummah (the Muslim community at large). The “new religious intellectuals”, a new generation of educated Muslims who immigrated to the West to study or work and who are active participants in online religious debates, are believed by scholars such as Roy Olivier to be attempting a reexamination and reinterpretation of their faith in light of modern realities (Roy, 2002).

In their book *Islam Dot Com*, Mohammed el-Nawawy and Sahar Khamis, two Egyptian scholars based in the USA, discuss the major role played by the new religious intellectuals in explaining Islam to non-Muslims in the politically tense post 9/11 era, as opposed to a lack of online interactivity on the part of traditional religious institutions and the *‘ulama*, who have limited themselves to mainly issuing fatwas (religious edicts) online. This contrast has created what the authors of *Islam Dot Com* call a divide in the “virtual Islamic

public sphere” (El-Nawawy and Khamis, 2009). The commonplace Muslim online narrative of al-Andalus (the Iberian Peninsula under Muslim rule) may be viewed as part of the discourse held by the new religious intellectuals within the “virtual ummah”, and al-Andalus as “imagined” by Muslims in general, as part of a “cultural collectivism” whose purpose is to allow them to reconstruct their identities as members of the ummah.

A case in point may be the discourse of *Fariq Andalusi* (An Andalusi Team), a group of young educated Muslims from different professional horizons and nationalities, some of whom are based in Europe or the USA, on *alandalushistory.com*, an important Muslim websites about the history of al-Andalus. Painting a rather romanticizing image of al-Andalus through many of its web articles, *Fariq Andalusi* stresses most of all the lost grandeur of Islamic civilization in Western Europe. Al-Andalus is thus generally presented as a part of *Dar al-*

Islam where Muslims thrived culturally and economically, had the upper hand militarily, and established unprecedented justice and freedom of religion.

This same idealistic representation of Muslim Iberia re-emerges time and again on social media. *Tārīḥ al-Andalus wa Ḥāḍiruhā* (The History and Present of al-Andalus) is a particularly nostalgic public Facebook group dedicated to al-Andalus as an Islamic cultural icon. Moderated by an Italy-based Arab self-proclaimed expert in all things al-Andalus, the group goes even so far as to express, in some of its posts, irredentist claims over modern-day Spain.

An argument can be advanced here that the aim of such triumphalist discourse on al-Andalus by a new generation of Muslim intellectuals is twofold: it is used as a compensatory tool within the societies of the MENA (Middle East and North Africa) region, whose socioeconomic conditions need to be urgently improved. And, in terms of “Self”,

as contrasted with its “Others”, it probably tries, whether within or without the geographical confines of the Muslim world, to counterbalance the effects of westernization, that is globalization, on Muslim identity on both the individual (the Muslim) and collective (ummah) levels.

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